

Potentiometric Studies of Some Bivalent Metal Chelates of 3-Aldehydosalicylic Acid-Aniline Schiff Base

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Manuscript received 17 August 1977, accepted 7 December 1977

Complexation equilibria of metal complexes of UO_2^{++} , Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} and Mn^{++} with 3-Aldehydosalicylic acid-aniline (abbreviated 3.ASAA) have been carried out potentiometrically. The stability constants of these chelates were determined in 30/70 (v/v) dioxane-water medium by Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique^{1,2} at 25° in a medium of 0.2M ionic strength.

THE chelating properties of 3.ASAA with some bivalent metals have been studied. But little attention has, however, been paid to determine the stability constants of these complexes of this compound. In the present communication the metal-ligand stability constants were determined by using Irving-Rossotti method³. The Job's method⁴ was applied to establish the composition conductometrically.

Materials

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. The dioxane⁵ and sodiumhydroxide⁶ free from carbondioxide were prepared. 0.1M perchloric acid was prepared by titrating it against standard NaOH. 2.0M sodium-perchlorate was prepared in double distilled water.

For potentiometric studies metal sulphates were used, while acetates of metals were used for separation of solid complexes.

Conductometric measurements were done with the help of Elico-conductivity bridge model. CM-82.

A Metrohm pH meter E-350 A with a wide range glass electrode in conjugation with a calomel electrode was used and calibrated at two pH; at 4.01 pH with potassium hydrogen phthalate and at 7.0 pH with potassium hydrogen phthalate and sodiumhydroxide buffers. All titrations were performed in 100 ml pyrex beaker equipped with stirrer. Quickfit glass assembly was used for the preparation of ligand.

Experimental and Results

Preparation of ligand: The ligand was prepared in the laboratory^{7,8} and was analysed for its purity before use.

Composition of the complexes: Job's method⁴ was employed to establish the composition of the complexes conductometrically. The results showed that complexes contain metal and the ligand in the ratio of 1:1. All measurements were done in 50% aqueous ethanol medium.

Potentiometric titrations: The following solutions were titrated separately (I) free $HClO_4$, (II) free $HClO_4 + \text{Ligand}$ and (III) free $HClO_4 + \text{Ligand} + \text{Metal}$. The ratio between metal and ligand was kept 1:6 to fulfill the maximum co-ordination number of the corresponding metal ions. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2M by the addition of an appropriate amount of 2M $NaClO_4$ solution.

The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the titration assembly containing the electrode.

The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by employing Irving-Rossotti equation⁹.

Calculation of stability constants: From the titration curve using the solution (I) and (II) \bar{n}_A values of the various pH values were calculated. The formation curve of proton-ligand curve was obtained by plotting a graph between \bar{n}_A and pH . The values $\log K_1H$ and $\log K_2H$ were determined by using various computational methods⁸. The values are reported as under (Table 1.)

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 3 ASAA

Method	$\log K_1H$	$\log K_2H$	$\log \beta_2H$
Interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values	10.10	4.05	14.15
Interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values	10.08	4.05	14.13
Mid Point Method	10.08	4.12	14.20
Mean	10.08	4.08	14.16

From the titration curve using the solution (II) and (III) \bar{n} values of the metal chelates were determined at various pH values. From this data the corresponding pL

were then calculated. The \bar{n} values plotted against the corresponding pL were to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria. The approximate values of $\log K_1$ were directly noted down from the curves and tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL LIGAND CHELATES

Metal	$\log K_1$
UO_2^{++}	6.95
Cu^{++}	5.64
Ni^{++}	5.26
Co^{++}	5.15
Mn^{++}	5.04

Discussion

The metal ligand curve has been found to be well separated from the titration curve which indicates that the liberation of protons is due to chelation. Possibility of metal ions to hydrolyse has been ignored as the complex is found to be stable in the pH range studied.

The stability constants of metal complexes of this ligand show the order $UO_2 > Cu > Ni > Co > Mn$. This confirms the validity of Irving-Williams¹⁰ order for these complexes.

It is evident from the conductometric and potentiometric studies that this ligand forms 1:1 complexes.

The Schiff base behaved as tridentate ligand with the metals and the tentative structure is ascertained as:

References

1. J. BJERRUM, Metal Ammine formation in solution (Hasse, Copenhagen), 1941.
2. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
3. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 2904.
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, (Paris), 1928, 9 (10), 113.
5. A. I. VOGEL, A textbook of practical organic chemistry (Longmans, Green & Co.), 1957.
6. N. ALLEN and G. W. LOW, *Ind. and Engg. Chem. Anal. Edition*, 1933, 5, 192.
7. J. DUFF and E. BILLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (London), 1932, 1987.
8. S. N. PODDAR, *Z. Anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1963, 322, 326.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3394.
10. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746.